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Stability of Binary and Ternary Complexes of Cadmium with some Amino Acids and Propionic Acid. A Polarographic Study

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IN continuation of previous work¹⁻³, the present study aims to find out the stability of binary and ternary complexes of Cd^{II} with glycine, α -alanine, L-valine, L-leucine, L-asparagine and L-glutamine as primary ligands and propionic acid as secondary ligand by polarographic technique.

Experimental

A.R. grade chemicals were used to prepare the solutions in conductivity water. The concentrations of metal ion, potassium nitrate and gelatin in the test solution are 1.0 mM, 1.0 M and 0.001% respectively. The purities of amino acids were checked by chromatographic method⁴ and the concentration of each amino acid varied in the range 1.0–10.0 mM.

The metal and ligands (amino acid and propionic acid) were taken in the ratio 1 : 40 and current-voltage curves were drawn. The maximum shift of $E_{1/2}$ was observed at pH 8.50 \pm 0.1 and hence this pH was selected for the investigation.

Current-voltage measurements were made on a manual polarograph using a Toshniwal pL-50 polyflex galvanometer. The capillary characteristics were $n^{2/3} t^{1/6} = 2.40 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ s}^{-1/2}$ at 60.0 cm (60.02 calculated)⁵ effective height of mercury. Nitrogen gas was passed through the solutions for deoxygenation before recording the current-voltage measurements. An Elico LI-10 needle type pH-meter was used to measure the pH which was adjusted at 8.50 \pm 0.1 with dilute solutions of sodium hydroxide and nitric acid as required. All the measurements were made at 25 \pm 0.1°. Stability constants were calculated by Lingane⁶ and Deford and Hume⁷ methods.

Results and Discussion

Cd^{II} gave a well-defined two-electron reversible reduction wave in KNO₃ and gelatin⁵. All the waves for the metal and its complexes were reversible and diffusion-controlled which were confirmed from the plots of $E_{d,e}$ vs $\log(i/i_a - i)$ and i_d vs \sqrt{h} , respectively.

Cd propionate system: The system was studied at pH 8.50 \pm 0.1 and $I=1.0 \text{ M}$ (KNO₃). All the waves were reversible and diffusion-controlled which were confirmed from $(E_{3/4} - E_{1/4}) = 30 \pm 1 \text{ mV}$ values and also the plots of $\log i/(i_a - i)$ vs $E_{d,e}$ and i_d vs \sqrt{h} , respectively. Lingane⁶ treatment of the data confirmed the formation of 1:1 and 1:2 complexes with stability constants $\log \beta_{01} = 2.46$ and $\log \beta_{02} = 3.90$ respectively.

Cd-amino acid-propionic acid system: This system was also studied at pH = 8.50 \pm 0.1 by keeping the concentration of propionic acid constant at 0.005 and 0.01 M while varying the concentration of each amino acid from 1.0 to 10.0 mM, and current-voltage curves were obtained. The values of $E_{1/2}$ increased with increase of the concentration of amino acid showing complexes formation for each of the constant concentration of propionic acid. The values of pK and stability of binary and ternary complexes⁸ of Cd^{II} with amino acids and propionic and are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1 – VALUES OF STABILITY CONSTANTS FOR BINARY AND TERNARY COMPLEXES OF Cd^{II}

System	pK ₂ ^H	pK ₁ ^H	log β_{10}	log β_{20}	log β_{30}	log β_{11}	log β_{12}	log β_{21}
[Cd-gly.-prop.]	2.40	9.30	4.30	7.60	9.64	6.56	8.97	9.37
[Cd- α -ala.-prop.]	2.50	9.40	4.23	7.46	9.43	6.40	8.75	9.15
[Cd-L-val.-prop.]	2.28	9.71	4.11	7.21	9.16	6.38	8.60	8.97
[Cd-L-leu.-prop.]	2.32	9.74	4.17	7.35	9.34	6.22	8.38	8.75
[Cd-L-glut.-prop.]	2.17	9.13	4.00	7.04	8.91	6.21	8.31	8.67
[Cd-L-asp.-prop.]	2.02	8.80	4.07	7.18	9.10	6.05	8.09	8.45

For comparison of simple and ternary complexes, it is convenient to calculate the values of mixing constants ($\log K_m$) by the equation⁹,

$$\log K_m = \log \beta_{11} - \frac{1}{2} [\log \beta_{02} + \log \beta_{20}]$$

which are 0.81, 0.72, 0.75, 0.66, 0.67 and 0.58 for [Cd-gly. prop.], [Cd- α -ala.-prop.], [Cd-L-leu.-prop.], [Cd-L-val.-prop.], [Cd-L-asp.-prop.] and [Cd-L-glut.-prop.] systems respectively, showing ternary complexes of Cd^{II} with amino acids. The trend of stabilities of complexes is L-glutamine < L-asparagine < L-valine < L-leucine < α -alanine < glycine, which might be a result of increase of side-chain of amino acids¹.

The sequence of stability constants for ternary complexes is the same as that for binary complexes.

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Formation Constants and Thermodynamic Parameters of Lanthanum(III), Gadolinium(III) and Dysprosium(III) Complexes with Thioacids

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IN view of the significant role of sulphur compounds, the present investigation deals with the study of formation constants and thermodynamics of rare earth metal ions with three thioacids, namely, 2-thiophene acetic acid (2-TPA), 3-thiophene acetic acid (3-TPA) and 3-(2-thienyl)acrylic acid (3-(2-TE)AA).

Experimental

The pH was recorded on a Eltop 3020 digital pH meter. All measurements were made in a thermostat maintained at the desired temperature ($\pm 0.05^\circ$). All metal salts (Sigma) used were converted to their perchlorates. The ligands (Aldrich) were of analytical grade. The formation constants and practical proton-ligand constants were obtained from the data obtained by titrating solutions containing (i) metal perchlorate solution (0.0005M) + thioacid (0.003M) + perchloric acid (0.004M), (ii) thioacid (0.003M) + perchloric acid (0.004M) and (i) perchloric acid (0.004M), maintained at a constant volume of 50 ml (in 50% dioxane-water medium) in each case, against standard potassium hydroxide solution (0.1M) at 25, 35 and 45° in a specially designed double-walled beaker. The experiments were performed in duplicate. The readings were found to be reproducible to ± 0.01 unit of pH. The ionic strength was maintained at 0.1M with sodium perchlorate solution.

Results and Discussion

The formation curves (\bar{n}_H vs pH) for the practical proton-ligand systems were found to be extended between 0 and 1 on the scale, which justifies monobasic nature of the thioacids. Three computational methods (a) interpolation and half-integral method, (b) linear plot method and (c) pointwise calculations, were used for evaluation of practical proton-ligand formation constant values (Table 1). The strength of acidity varies as

TABLE 1 - PROTON-LIGAND FORMATION CONSTANTS OF LIGANDS AT VARIOUS TEMPERATURES*

Solvent: 50% dioxane, $\mu = 0.1 M$ (NaClO₄)

Ligand	$\log K_1^H$		
	25°C	35°C	45°C
2-TPA	(a) 3.58	3.72	3.78
	(b) 3.58	3.73	3.78
	(c) 3.60	3.73	3.78
	(3.59)	(3.73)	(3.78)
3-TPA	(a) 3.74	3.79	4.15
	(b) 3.73	3.78	4.16
	(c) 3.75	3.80	4.15
	(3.74)	(3.79)	(4.15)
3-(2-TE)AA	(a) 3.79	4.14	4.38
	(b) 3.79	4.15	4.39
	(c) 3.80	4.15	4.39
	(3.79)	(4.15)	(4.39)

* (a) = Half-integral method, (b) = pointwise calculations, (c) = linear plot method; mean values in parenthesis.

2-TPA > 3-TPA > 3-(2-TE)AA. The thioacids differ in the position of RCOOH group in 2-TPA and 3-TPA and additional CH=CH grouping is present in 3-(2-TE)AA. The decrease in acidity in 3-TPA may be due to less negative inductive effect in 3-TPA as compared to 2-TPA and further decrease